

A SINGLE CASE STUDY ON MANAGEMENT OF SCALP PSORIASIS THROUGH
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ABSTRACT

Psoriasis is a chronic non-communicable proliferative autoimmune skin disease which affects 2-3% of worldwide population. This skin condition has significant comorbidities and a profound psychosocial impact. *Ayurveda* includes all skin diseases under the broad term "*Kushta*". Here an effort was made to treat a male patient suffering from scalp psoriasis through *Ayurveda* with a view point of *Eka Kushta*, where *Shodhana* was included as prime treatment modality. This case report showcases consolidated treatment protocol which brought about tremendous improvement in the condition of patient.

KEYWORDS: *Eka Kushta*, Scalp Psoriasis, *Ayurveda*, *Kushta*, *Shodhana*.**INTRODUCTION**

Psoriasis is a chronic and inflammatory skin disease with reactive abnormal epidermal differentiation and hyper proliferation that affects 4-5% of the global population.^[1] It can occur at any age, although it most commonly appears for the first time between the ages of 15 and 25 years. Approximately one third of people with psoriasis report being diagnosed before age 20.^[2] Psoriasis can manifest in five different types: plaque, guttate, inverted, pustular, and erythrodermic.^[3] of psoriasis are plaque psoriasis, also called psoriasis vulgaris. Usually, it appears as white scales on top of red spots. The backs of the forearms, shins, the area around the navel, and the scalp are the body parts most frequently effected.^[4] Aside from the typical intertriginous regions such as the armpits, groin, beneath the breasts, and around the navel, inverse psoriasis can also affect the scalp, palms, and soles. The lesions are well-defined plaques, but due to their location, they might appear moist and lack scales. About 90% of instances.^[5] The scalp is one of the most commonly affected sites in psoriasis. However, due of difficulties with the administration of medication, scalp psoriasis can be challenging to cure. Patient's quality of life must be improved with effective treatment plans for scalp psoriasis.^[6]

In *Ayurveda* skin diseases can be correlated with *Kushta*. *Kushtha* is a chronic disease which presents with ugly color/ complexion/ texture and altered tactile perceptions of the skin. *Tvacha* (skin) is a seat of *Sparshanrndriya*. It carries the sensation of touch and it also covers the internal part of the body. *Tvacha* (skin) is '*Panchbhautik*' but out of them *Vayumahabhuta* is prominent one.^[7]

Kushthroga which is classified into two groups- *Mahakushtha* and *Kshudrakushtha*. Minor skin diseases are known as *Kshudra Kushta*. *Kshudra Kushta* can be classified into eleven and one among them is *Eka Kushta*. Vitiation of *Kapha-Dosha* is the main factor behind *Eka Kushta*. Here the lesions are spread over an extended area of the skin.^[8]

Shodhana and *Shamana chikitsa* are mentioned for the management of *Kushta*. *Shodhana chikitsa* is based on *Panchkarma* therapy whereas *shaman* is included with oral medication and local application.

CASE REPORT

Name: XYZ Age: 22 yrs

Present ComplaintsA 22 years old male patient came to *Kayachikitsa* OPD

with chief complaints of

- 1) Patches all over the head with dandruff.
- 2) Scaling of scalp skin.
- 3) Itching over the scalp.

Patient had above complaints since childhood. No H/O DM/HTN, Asthma.

The patient was having above mentioned complaints since childhood. These symptoms aggravated when he got into adolescence. For this patient took treatment from different Allopathy doctors but got no relief, then he came to CSSAS hospital in *Kayachikitsa* department OPD for further Ayurvedic management.

Routine blood investigation was done to rule out any possible associated disorder. There was no past history of any type of addiction. He was diagnosed with *Ekakustha* (Scalp psoriasis).

Family History: No such history of skin disorder.

Past History: No significant past history.

Personal history • Occupation- Student

- *Ahara*- intake of junk food, spicy and oily diet.
- *Vihara*- sedentary lifestyle
- *Nidra* –Disturbed due to itching
- History of Daytime sleep (2hrs)
- *Vyasana*: no any history of any addiction.

On Examination

Nadi: 78/ min. *Mala*: 1 time a day *Mootra*: *Prakruta*

Jivha: *Saam*

Agni: *Manda*

TREATMENT PLAN

- Patient was treated with *Shodhana Chikitsa* (*Virechana*) and *Shamana chikitsa*.

Shodhana chikitsa

Patient was examined for *dosha*, *bala*, *agni* and *prakriti* for fitness of *Virechan* and written consent was taken before starting procedure.

Sr. no.	Dates	Treatment	Drug	Dose	Duration
1	21/03/2026-25/03/2026	<i>Deepana-Pachana</i>	<i>Chitrakadi vati</i> <i>Raktapachak vati</i>	2 tablets each twice day before food	5 days
2	26/03/2026-01/04/2026	<i>Snehapana</i>	<i>Mahatikta Ghrita</i>	1st – 5ml 2nd –10 ml 3rd – 20 ml 4th – 40 ml 5th – 40 ml 6th – 60 ml 7th – 80 ml	7 days
3.	02/04/2026-04/04/2026	<i>Abhyanga Swedana</i>	<i>Tila taila</i> <i>Sarwanga sweda</i> with <i>Dasamoola kwatha</i>	8 th , 9 th and 10 th day	3 days
4.	05/04/2026	<i>Virechana</i>	<i>Trivrut avaleha</i>	11 th day	1 day
5.	05/04/2026-07/04/2026	<i>Samsarjana Karma</i>	<i>MudgaYushadi karma</i>	Morning and evening two times	3 days

Shaman chikitsa

Sr.no	Drug	Dose
1	<i>Arogyavardhini</i>	2 tablets twice a day
2	<i>Haridrakand churna+ Gandhak rasayan</i>	2gm+1 tab -SOS (when itching is increased)
3.	<i>Raktapachak vati</i>	2 tablets twice a day
4.	<i>Jatyadi taila+ Durdurapatradi taila</i>	Local application

Diet and hygiene

- Very strict Diet regime
- Lifestyle changes
- Stress management

- Patient was advised not to take sour, bitter, spicy food as well as junk food, fried items and curd. He was also advised to have *Pranayama* regularly.

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

Assessment criteria

Sign & Symptoms	Before treatment	After <i>shodhana</i>	After <i>Shamana</i>
<i>Aswedanam</i>	2	1	0
<i>Keshapatan</i>	3	1	0
<i>Matsyashakalopamam</i>	3	2	0

Shirokandu	3	1	0
Darunaka	2	1	0
Auspitz Sign	-	-	-
Candle Grease Sign	+	-	-

Before treatment

After treatment

DISCUSSION

In Ayurveda classics, all skin diseases described under heading of *Kushtha*. Among them *Ekakushtha* is type of *Kshudrakushtha*.^[9] According to *Acharya Charaka*, *Ekakushtha* characterized by *Aswedana* (anhydrotic / hypohydratic lesions), *Mahavastu* (covering of large surface area), *Matsyashakalavat* (scaly lesions) *Twacha*.^[10] *Ekakushtha* can be correlated with psoriasis due to resemblance of signs and symptoms. Treatment of *Kushta* includes *panchakarma* with *purvakarma* starting with *snehana*.

Shodhananga Snehapana, which is the process of administering *Sneha dravyas* (unctuous substances) prior to performing *Shodhana* (detoxification) therapy i.e. *Virechana* (purgative therapy). The primary goal of *Snehapana* is to prepare the body for the *Shodhana* procedure. The *Shodhana* therapies (such as *Vamana* and *Virechana*) are aimed at expelling the accumulated *Doshas* (biological energies) from the body. However, for these procedures to be effective, the body must be lubricated and softened so that the *Doshas* can be more easily mobilized and expelled.^[11]

Action of *Virechana yoga* because of its *Vyavayi Guna* gets absorbed quickly and due to its *Virya*, it reaches to *Hridaya*, *Dhammani* and all of the macro and micro channels of the body. Its *Vikasi Guna* causes softening and loosening of the bond by *Dhatu Shaithilya Karma*. *Ushna guna* causes liquification of *Dosha Sanghata*. It breaks the *Mala* and *Doshas* in micro form due to its *Tikshana Guna*. Due to *Sukshma Guna* by reaching in micro channels, disintegrates endogenic toxins, which are then excreted through micro channels. *Virechana* occurs mainly due to *Prabhava*, *Prithvi* and *Jala* constitution and presence of *Sara Guna*.^[12]

Arogyavardhini vati is a classical herbo-mineral Ayurvedic preparation has the ability of balancing

Tridosha, destroying all types of skin disorders, analgesic, wound healing, and antipruritic properties, which helps in reducing symptoms of *Kushta*. Bitter taste, dry, and light properties are useful in destroying all skin disorders. Complexion-strengthening action of sweet properties improves the complexion of the skin and bestows ideal skin texture.^[13]

Haridra Khanda is described as effective in *Kañḍū* (itching), *Dadru* (ringworm), *Viṣphoṭa* (blisters), *Udarda*, and *Koṭha*, & is especially regarded as "*Kañḍūnam Parama Auśadham*" (foremost remedy for itching).^[14] *Gandhak rasayan* mainly acts on skin, blood and it is *Rasayana* in action. So, it more or less acts on all *Doshas* and *Dhatus*. *Gandhak* is *Ushna Veeryatmaka* and *Katu Rasa Vipaki* so acts as best *Kaphghna* and *Kledaghna*. *Gandhak Rasayan* helps to destroy the *Samprapti* (pathogenesis) of *Kshudra Kushtha* due to its *Ushnaveerya* and *Katukashaya Rasa*.^[15] *Raktapachak vati* is a herbal formulation which is helpful in *raktapradoshaja vikar* with contents of *Patol*, *Sariva*, *Musta*, *Patha* and *Kutaki*.^[16]

The significant results in *Kandu* and *Raukshyakrit Sphutan* by *Dhurdhurpatradi Tailam* can be attributed to *Dhattur*, an *Upvisha* with its *Kaphahara*, *Katu vipaka*, *Krimighna*, *Ropan karma* pacified the *Doshas*, also due to Atropine, Scopolamine, saponins and Flavonoids, the chemical constituents of *Datura metel* Linn. acts as an antimicrobial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory and anti-allergic, thereby arresting the microbial proliferation, sebum secretion and excessive sweat, also, normalizing the skin barrier functions by anti-oxidants.^[17] The *Jatyadi Taila* have *Tikta*, *Kashaya Rasas*, and *Laghu*, *Ruksha Gunas* make up the majority. *Jatyadi Taila* has the qualities of *Vrana Shodhana*, *Ropana*, *Pootihara*, and *Vedanasthapana*. It is *Tikta* and *Kashaya Rasa Pradhana*, both of which are *Pitta Kaphahara*.^[18]

CONCLUSION

Ekakushtha characterized by *Aswedana* (anhydrotic / hypohydratic lesions), *Mahavastu* (covering of large surface area), *Matsyashakalavat* (scaly lesions) *Twacha*. *Ekakushtha* can be correlated with psoriasis due to resemblance of signs and symptoms. *Chikitsa* of *kushta* mainly include *panchakarma*. *Panchakarma* therapy aims at the elimination of excessive *Doshas* from the body to maintain the state of health for a longer duration, while the *Shamana* therapy is for suppression of vitiated *Doshas* within the body. *Virechana* is one of the *Panchakarma* therapies wherein purgation is induced by drugs and it specifically aims at the elimination of excessive *Pitta Dosh* from the body. *Shamana dravyas* includes those which are *tridosha shamak*, *raktaprasadana*, *twak prasadana*. The findings of this case report suggest that with above Ayurvedic intervention in scalp psoriasis may be managed successfully. This would be very helpful and also serve as a guide for the practitioners for the practical application of skin diseases with Ayurvedic perspective.

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